

EXAMINATION OF SELF-CONFIDENCE OF INDIVIDUALS INTERESTED IN MOUNTAINEERING AND SEARCH AND RESCUE

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Abstract:

The aim of this study is to examine the self-confidence relevance of the individuals who mountaineer and individuals who are part of search and rescue operations. Two hundred seventy nine persons voluntarily participated in the research. The research data was collected using the self-confidence scale developed by Akin (2007). There are a total of 33 articles in the scale. The scale is composed of two factors. These are the two sub dimensions being interior self-confidence and exterior self-confidence. The data collected was analyzed through the statistical package program (SPSS 16.0) and the results were interpreted. In our study, the Cronbach's Alpha Value of the scale was calculated as 0.89. The One Way ANOVA and T-test were used in the evaluation of the research data. In the research, as regards the gender, branch, experience, age and marital status, meaningful correlations were identified. As a result, athletes who performed search and rescue have higher self-confidence than those who mountaineer. Since both fields involve risky activities, it is recommended for the athletes who are involved in outdoor sports to be encouraged to get into search and rescue operations. Regular activities and training would improve self-confidence.

Keywords: mountaineering, search and rescue, self-confidence

1. Introduction

Sport is the vehicle which consumes the potential energy in the individuals of society in the most helpful way as body and mind, enables the construction of healthy

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relationships in individuals and in society, leads the person to happiness in a balanced manner in various cases and brings the society discipline, respect for rules and individuals believing in social peace (Güven, 1999) as an aspect of game type (Alıncak, 2016a; Alıncak, 2016b). In parallel with this, the outdoor sports attract an increasing attention in recent years. Today, making use of leisure time is becoming a life style in these times where stress has escalated. For this reason, there are various programs and projects for increasing the leisure time activities and enhancing the range of valuing leisure time. In this respect, the leisure activities constructed their own philosophy in a way to support the psychological, social and physical values the individual possesses. The activities in which people are, as active or passive, involved assist individuals to be included in the society by encompassing the efforts that affect the life style in their field of occupation, and enhance the shared life (Yerlisu Lapa and Ardahan, 2009).

The interest in outdoor sports has been gradually increasing in our country and the field of application of this sport has varied. These sports may include mountaineering, hiking, paragliding, water sports, etc. (Kuru, 2000). Turkey offers quite beneficent opportunities for many outdoor sports. The people who tend towards alternative sports are now choosing between the sport branches which give them pleasure, entertain them and push their limits (Voigt, 1998). Mountaineering, the most preferred one, was defined by Pomfret (2006). As a type of nature-based adventure tourism which comprises ice and rock climbing and mountain hiking in mountain regions all around the world. Mountaineering means knowing well the nature of the mountain. It also imposes the condition of having the ability to overcome the possible challenges (Moynier, 2004). The increase in this type of hazardous sportive activities and the resulting accidents and natural disasters prioritized search and rescue. The search and rescue operations are the operations carried out to find and rescue the people in danger in mountains, deserts, sea, forest and other tough regions (Stone, 1975). As can be understood by the definitions, mountaineering as well as search and rescue are operations which involve risk and danger. As in the whole world, occurrence of disasters has increased in our country as well. Damaging the nature, improper urbanization and an unconscious society insensitive to the environment all set the ground for disasters.

Such a risk of disaster brought up the need for search and rescue personnel. Many rescuers put themselves in jeopardy without hesitating. It is also thought that the feeling underlying this is self-confidence. On the other hand, the increasing interest in outdoor sports, particularly in mountaineering, increased the probability of having accidents in mountains. Passions such as for the wild nature, adventure, being close to the nature, physical exercise, nature view, desire for being alone, socialization, risk-

taking, challenge, entertainment and pursuing uncertainty are pursued by outdoor athletes (Carr, 1998). In light of this information, “self-confidence” which underlies our research becomes an important matter in search and rescue.

Inherently, we all have the motive to survive instead of die when our lives are in danger (McManners, 2009). The challenging activities such as climbing mountains or performing search and rescue require some personality traits. Self-confidence is one of these traits. Feltz (1988). Defined self-confidence as “rather than a general trait, the belief of an individual to fulfill a specific activity in a successful way and to trust his/her own judgments, abilities, power and decisions”. Self-confidence is a necessity to succeed in a sportive performance (McAuley and Gill, 1983). The issue of self-confidence has been a subject of analysis especially in risky sports. It is told in the accidents that particularly in dangerous sports such as mountaineering, extreme self-confidence also leads to fatal mistakes (Krakauer, 2006). The safety measures against the risk seek to eliminate the existing danger in the field of activity and are subject to careful evaluation (Maningas and Simpson, 2003). It comes to mind that the emotion of self-confidence is effective in risk-taking. Although the number of injuries and deaths are high in outdoor sports which does not tolerate mistakes, the popularity of these high-risk sports has ever increased in western societies. Therefore, it is important for those who engage in high-risk sports to be aware of the factors underlying the behavioral strategies towards various risks (Martha et al., 2009). This places self-confidence which is one of the influential traits, at a more critical level. On the other hand, self-confidence depends on whether the person feels accepted and valued by others (Jahanbakhsh, Jomehri, Mujembari, 2015). In other words, self-confidence is influenced by society or groups. Self-confidence has been an important element for many outdoor sports. Researchers have tried to examine self-confidence in different ways. Martin et al. (1999) put forward that using visuals is effective in improving sportive performance. For example, watching the image of a master climber who climbs over a difficult rock surface may be effective in improving the performance. According to this, visuals are used in coping with challenging situations, particularly in enhancing self-competence and self-confidence (Jones et al., 2002; Martin et al, 1999). As it is understood, self-confidence is a significant factor for mountaineering and search and rescue.

In the light of the information given above, our research has an important place since there are not much research available concerning self-confidence of athletes who perform search and rescue. Since mountaineering and search and rescue involves a stressful process under tough conditions, it is important to know how much self-confidence is influential. Every passing year, the number of those who engage in

outdoor tourism and outdoor sports increase and disasters occur for various reasons. The emergency cases pointed out the requirement for educated and equipped athletes. The results of the study are expected to guide the authorities and executives. In parallel with this, this research is conducted in order to examine self-confidence of those who engage in mountaineering and search and rescue.

Method

The geographical condition in Turkey offers limitless possibilities for mountaineering. This increased the number of mountaineering clubs. In parallel with this, the number of people who engage in mountaineering also increased. This situation makes it difficult to work and access the athletes in different regions of Turkey. For this reason, the questionnaire used in the study was conducted in the camps of mountaineering clubs, in trainings and on athletes who came for mountain climbing.

Besides, the changing climate conditions and the resulting increase in the number of disasters emphasized the importance of people and associations who perform search and rescue operations. In such cases, trained personnel are of vital importance. In our study, the voluntary individuals who regularly attend training and search and rescue operations were also included in the sample group. A total of 279 athletes from different regions and clubs attended the research. In the study, the questionnaire technique among the quantitative research techniques was used.

Population and Sample

The research population consists of those who engage in mountaineering and the voluntary people who engage in search and rescue associations. Taking into account those who mountaineer and the difficulty in accessing the large number of sports clubs, the research was limited to athletes who regularly and actively attend mountaineering activities. For search and rescue associations, those associations which frequently conduct trainings and operations were preferred. The scales delivered by hand were applied by the researcher during camping, climbing and training. The research was limited to voluntary search and rescue associations. Access to volunteers who engage in search and rescue and who are educated made the research difficult. The sample of the research consists of the athletes who actively and regularly mountaineer and who voluntarily carry out search and rescue operations as member of an association. Both groups consist of trained athletes.

The participants are composed of 211 (75.6%) men and 68 (24.4%) women. 65.9% (184) of the research group is university graduate. 65.9% of participants is single. The

age group with the largest percentage in the research is the group aged 41 and above (61 persons, 21.9%). One hundred seventy nine mountaineers and 100 athletes, who engage in search and rescue, participated in the research. Forty three percent (120) of the participants has mountaineering or search and rescue history of 1-4 years.

Data Collection Tool

The self-confidence scale used in the research is developed by Akin (2007). As a result of the factor analysis, 33 items under two factors were obtained. The scale consists of two sub dimensions being internal self-confidence and external self-confidence. Analyzing the items fewer than two factors obtained, the items under the first factor were identified to be related to self-confidence of individuals towards the individuals themselves and this factor was considered under the name internal self-confidence. The items under this factor evaluates the traits of the individual such as self-love, self-consciousness, setting explicit goals, possessing the ability of positive thinking, recognizing strengths and weaknesses.

Since the items under the second factor are more related to the self-confidence of individuals regarding their external environment and social life, this factor was named as external self-confidence. The items under the dimension of external self-confidence include traits such as easy communication, sound self-expression, control of emotions and ability to take risks. The high score from this scale which does not include any negative item indicates a high level of self-confidence. In the self-confidence scale, a score lower than 2.5 indicate low self-confidence, between 2.5 and 3.5 indicates medium and above 3.5 indicates high self-confidence. The total number of items in Self-Confidence Scale is 33. The highest score that can be received from this scale prepared using the 5-degree Likert type is 165 and lowest score is 33. The scale is never scored in such manner as Never (1), Seldom (2), Often (3), Usually (4) and Always (5) (Akin, 2007).

Data Collection

Information such as the purpose of the research, how the questionnaire form is to be marked and what should be paid attention in marking and the name, surname and title of the person conducting the research and of the consultant and the name of the organization where they work was given on top of the questionnaire forms used in the research. The scale was applied on the mountaineers who came to climb the Anti-Taurus Mountains on dates August 25 to October 20, 2014 in the International Mountaineering Association Coherence Camp of Zirve Mountain and Outdoor Sports Club in Kaynaklar, Izmir on December 26-27, 2014 in the International Petzl Roc Trip

climbing fest carried out in Olimpos, Antalya on October 16-19, 2014. The scale applied on search and rescue groups was applied on the members of SAR search and rescue association on dates August 25-26, 2015 in the trainer training camp of AKUT search and rescue association carried out in Olimpos, Antalya on November 13-16, 2014. The scale was applied by the researcher during climbing and in training camps on those who voluntarily participated in the research.

Reliability and Validity Analyses of Data Collection Tool

For general reliability, Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was calculated, like some other studies (Cinpolat et al., 2016). The most common method used in the examination of reliability is Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient. In our study, Cronbach's Alpha Value of the scale was calculated as 0.89. Significance was defined as $p \leq 0.05$.

Data Evaluation

The data collected through self-confidence scale and demographic information questionnaire was analyzed through the statistical package program (SPSS 16.0) and the results were interpreted. Firstly, the demographic information and, for having an idea about questions, the descriptor statistics including arithmetic mean, standard deviation, frequency and percentage distribution were presented, like some other studies (Abakay, 2013; Polat et al., 2011; Yıkılmaz et al., 2015). The data showed normal and homogeneous distribution. In the analysis of athletes' self-confidence, in the case of two groups in comparing quantitative data, in intergroup comparison, the Independent Samples t test was used. In case of more than two groups, the one way ANOVA test was used in intergroup comparison of parameters. Significance was defined as $p \leq 0.05$, like some other studies (Özdal, 2016a; Özdal, 2016b; Bilgiç et al., 2016).

Findings

Table 1: The Distribution of Athletes' Self-confidence Value According to Branch Variable

	Sport Branch	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P
Internal Self-Confidence	Mountaineering	179	4,0891	,45176	-4,383	,000
	Search and Rescue	100	4,3224	,37637		
External Self-Confidence	Mountaineering	179	4,0765	,46458	-2,762	,006
	Search and Rescue	100	4,2212	,32426		
Total Points	Mountaineering	179	4,0830	,43594	-3,818	,000
	Search and Rescue	100	4,2733	,32352		

Table 2: Comparison of Athletes' Self-confidence According to Gender Variable

	Sport Branch	Female	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P
Internal Self-Confidence	Mountaineering	49	3,9928	,50497	-3,051	,003
	Search and Rescue	19	4,3746	,32587		
External Self-Confidence	Mountaineering	49	3,9898	,47244	-3,125	,003
	Search and Rescue	19	4,3454	,23420		
Total Points	Mountaineering	49	3,9913	,46309	-3,249	,002
	Search and Rescue	19	4,3604	,27568		
	Sport Branch	Male	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P
Internal Self-Confidence	Mountaineering	130	4,1253	,42648	-3,166	,002
	Search and Rescue	81	4,3101	,38808		
External Self-Confidence	Mountaineering	130	4,1091	,45917	-1,408	,161
	Search and Rescue	81	4,1921	,33654		
Total Points	Mountaineering	130	4,1175	,42195	-2,453	,015
	Search and Rescue	81	4,2529	,33196		

In Table 2, the points obtained by the research group in self-confidence sub dimension and the results of Independent Samples t test according to gender variable were given. 68 women and 211 men participated in the research. The women and men who perform search and rescue have higher self-confidence than women and men who mountaineer. According to gender, no significant correlation was observed ($P < 0.05$).

Table 3: Comparison of Athletes' Self-confidence According to Their Experience

	Sport Branch	Experience	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P
Internal Self-Confidence	Mountaineering	1-4 Year	82	4,1011	,44050	-,792	,430
	Search and Rescue		38	4,1579	,35188		
External Self-Confidence	Mountaineering	1-4 Year	82	4,0968	,45077	-,679	,498
	Search and Rescue		38	4,1694	,36521		
Total Points	Mountaineering	1-4 Year	82	4,0990	,47974	-,828	,410
	Search and Rescue		38	4,1635	,36528		
	Sport Branch	Experience	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P
Internal Self-Confidence	Mountaineering	5-9 Year	43	4,0561	,47908	-3,848	,000
	Search and Rescue		29	4,4544	,34583		
External Self-Confidence	Mountaineering	5-9 Year	43	4,0131	,43292	-3,624	,001
	Search and Rescue		29	4,3491	,30183		
Total Points	Mountaineering	5-9 Year	43	4,0352	,43833	-3,966	,000

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	Search and Rescue		29	4,4033	,29134		
	Sport Branch	Experience	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P
Internal Self-Confidence	Mountaineering		23	4,2481	,44338	-2,469	,018
	Search and Rescue		17	4,5398	,23181		
External Self-Confidence	Mountaineering	9-13 Year	23	4,2826	,47928	,171	,865
	Search and Rescue		17	4,2610	,23200		
Total Points	Mountaineering		23	4,2648	,43110	-1,268	,212
	Search and Rescue		17	4,4046	,16281		
	Sport Branch	Experience	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P
Internal Self-Confidence	Mountaineering		25	3,9365	,43423	-2,263	,029
	Search and Rescue		16	4,2426	,40349		
External Self-Confidence	Mountaineering	14-18 Year	25	3,9000	,39487	-1,511	,139
	Search and Rescue		16	4,0703	,26991		
Total Points	Mountaineering		25	3,9188	,40474	-2,006	,052
	Search and Rescue		16	4,1591	,31926		

In Table 3, the points obtained by research group in the sub dimensions of self-confidence and the results of Independent Samples t test according to experience were given. Six mountaineers with 19 or more years of experience also participated in the research. There are no athletes with 19 or more years of experience in search and rescue. A significant correlation was observed between search and rescue attendees with 5-9 years of experience and mountaineers with 5-9 years of experience. Search and rescue attendees with 5-9 years of experience have higher self-confidence than mountaineers. Moreover, significant differences were also encountered in the internal self-confidence of those with 9-13 and 14-18 years of experience ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4: Comparison of Athletes' Self-confidence Values According to age Variable

	Sport Branch	Age	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P
Internal Self-Confidence	Mountaineering		7	3,9076	,36397	-1,484	,160
	Search and Rescue		9	4,1373	,25641		
External Self-Confidence	Mountaineering	16-20 Age	7	3,7946	,45172	-1,815	,091
	Search and Rescue		9	4,1181	,25664		
Total Points	Mountaineering		7	3,8528	,38188	-1,771	,098
	Search and Rescue		9	4,1279	,23850		
	Sport Branch	Age	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P
Internal Self-Confidence	Mountaineering	21-25 Age	43	4,0958	,35434	- ,985	,329

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	Search and Rescue		16	4,1985	,36126		
External Self-Confidence	Mountaineering		43	4,0669	,45222	-0,732	,467
	Search and Rescue		16	4,1602	,38458		
Total Points	Mountaineering		43	4,0817	,36791	-0,922	,361
	Search and Rescue		16	4,1799	,35208		
	Sport Branch	Age	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P
Internal Self-Confidence	Mountaineering		40	4,1912	,48813	-2,874	,006
	Search and Rescue		14	4,5882	,27783		
External Self-Confidence	Mountaineering	26-30 Age	40	4,1828	,43999	-2,705	,009
	Search and Rescue		14	4,5179	,23568		
Total Points	Mountaineering		40	4,1871	,45249	-2,875	,006
	Search and Rescue		14	4,5541	,24802		
	Sport Branch	Age	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P
Internal Self-Confidence	Mountaineering		30	4,0451	,53327	-0,869	,389
	Search and Rescue		16	4,1765	,38603		
External Self-Confidence	Mountaineering	31-35 Age	30	4,0000	,51145	-1,619	,113
	Search and Rescue		16	4,2188	,23049		
Total Points	Mountaineering		30	4,0232	,50158	-1,276	,209
	Search and Rescue		16	4,1970	,28448		
	Sport Branch	Age	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P
Internal Self-Confidence	Mountaineering		22	4,1337	,63229	-0,194	,847
	Search and Rescue		21	4,1653	,40096		
External Self-Confidence	Mountaineering	36-40 Age	22	4,1761	,65965	,891	,378
	Search and Rescue		21	4,0357	,30076		
Total Points	Mountaineering		22	4,1543	,63426	,334	,740
	Search and Rescue		21	4,1025	,32616		
	Sport Branch	Age	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P
Internal Self-Confidence	Mountaineering		37	4,0143	,30578	-7,246	,000
	Search and Rescue		24	4,5539	,24648		
External Self-Confidence	Mountaineering	41 Age and older	37	4,0287	,28090	-3,465	,001
	Search and Rescue		24	4,2917	,30265		
Total Points	Mountaineering		37	4,0213	,25682	-6,284	,000
	Search and Rescue		24	4,4268	,22851		

In Table 4, the points that the research group obtained in the self-confidence sub dimensions and the results according to age variable were given. In the study, a significant correlation was observed between mountaineers and search and rescue attendees aged 26-30 and aged 41 or above ($P < 0.05$). It is seen that the averages of search

and rescue attendees are higher. Those who perform search and rescue operations have higher self-confidence.

Table 5: Comparison of Athletes' Self-confidence Values According to Marital Status

	Sport Branch	Marital Status (Married)	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P
Internal Self-Confidence	Mountaineering	39	4,1252	,50044	-3,039	,003
	Search and Rescue	56	4,3960	,36821		
External Self-Confidence	Mountaineering	39	4,1378	,40509	-1,440	,154
	Search and Rescue	56	4,2478	,33646		
Total Points	Mountaineering	39	4,1313	,42998	-2,498	,014
	Search and Rescue	56	4,3241	,32230		
	Sport Branch	Marital Status (Single)	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P
Internal Self-Confidence	Mountaineering	140	4,0790	,43865	-2,045	,042
	Search and Rescue	44	4,2286	,36969		
External Self-Confidence	Mountaineering	140	4,0594	,47977	-1,665	,098
	Search and Rescue	44	4,1875	,30855		
Total Points	Mountaineering	140	4,0695	,43816	-1,951	,053
	Search and Rescue	44	4,2087	,31696		

In Table 5, the points obtained by the research group in the sub dimension of self-confidence and the results according to marital status were given. In the study, it is seen that married search and rescue attendees have higher average in internal self-confidence and in total. For single persons, the significant correlation was observed only in internal self-confidence ($P < 0.05$).

Discussion and Conclusion

In our study, the differences between individuals who perform mountaineering sports and who perform search and rescue operations were identified. Mountaineering and search and rescue operations involve high risks and require a high level of training and experience. Considering the dangerous cases and risk arising from this situation, the manner in which persons behave during climbing or in a search and rescue operation gains an important size. Without a doubt, factors such as decision-making, acting quickly, team work, self-confidence and leadership during these activities are influential. In risky activities such as mountaineering and search and rescue, the fact that it should be pointed out how to cope with problems and how to act when faced

with such situations and the fact that this field lacks literature add importance to this research.

Self-confidence is important in mountaineering as in any sport branch. In mountaineering, the risk decreases when the necessary trainings are obtained and the difficulty limits are known. Likewise, search and rescue operations also require training and involve exercise in order not to forget the abilities. When the necessary training is obtained, it was thought that self-confidence will be prominent as a factor which would create details.

In the study, an advanced level of correlation was observed between those who perform mountaineering sports and those who perform search and rescue operations (Table 1) ($p < 0.01$). The self-confidence of those who perform search and rescue operations are higher than those who perform mountaineering. Akin (2007) divided self-confidence in two sub dimensions. For both internal and external self-confidence, search and rescue attendees have higher self-confidence. Internal self-confidence reflects the traits of the individual such as self-love, self-knowledge, setting explicit goals, possessing the ability of positive thinking, being aware of strengths and weaknesses, easily communicating with others, sound self-expression, emotion control and risk taking (Akin, 2007). In the study, the reason for the self-confidence of those who perform search and rescue operations to be higher is thought to be related to experience, training and being ready for emergency cases. Training and experience is, of course, also important in mountaineering. But in search and rescue operations, it is a matter of human life. It is thought that this difference is a factor increasing self-confidence. Personality traits are important in high risk sport branches. In his study, Gürer (2012) highlighted that those who perform search and rescue operations are also interested in any outdoor sports and also highlighted the importance of self-confidence. Self-confidence and the common characteristics of both branches might be the reason for mountaineers to also engage in search and rescue. The reason is that both mountaineering and search and rescue are activities that involve risk and excitement and require making snap decisions when necessary. Mountaineering sport and search and rescue operations contain challenging circumstances. In their study, McGrane et al. (2015) observed significant and positive correlation between physical self-confidence and sportive competence. This result supports the results in our study in terms of the importance of self-confidence for sport. The self-confidence performance shows up as a determinant factor.

In our research, significant correlations were observed in terms of gender (Table 2). In both women and men, the self-confidence of those who perform search and rescue operations is higher than that of mountaineers. As mentioned before, making vital

decisions is a critical detail for search and rescue attendees. The researchers mentioned that women have more limited opportunities in recreational activities due to the roles they assume (Manning, 1999). The matter of time is another topic that should be researched. It is known that men perform outdoor activities more than women due their social role. In many studies, it was deduced that gender affects motivation in recreational activities and men are more active and comfortable in mostly recreational preferences due to the structures supported by social institutions such as family, job and social habits (Ardahan and Yerlisu Lapa, 2011).

Jones and Chairman (2005) addressed the need for the search and rescue leader to interpret every case where he/she faces a problem as a life and death case. It is thought that the reasons for the high level of self-confidence in male and female search and rescue attendees are the fact that they act as a team, their wide equipment and use of technology. Different conclusions were also encountered in researches. In her study, Lois (2003) considered the gender difference in search and rescue attendees and arrived at the conclusion that male attendees are more experienced than female ones. She also stated that men feel more comfortable than female in the environment they are in. This supports the self-confidence of search and rescue attendees. Besides, it is known that mountaineering is a more individual sport. It is known that, in case of an accident, the mountaineer has no one else to receive help other than his/her partner and that he/she is supposed to tackle with vital situations on his/her own. These kinds of situations might affect the self-confidence of those who engage in mountaineering.

Huey et al. (2007) examined the age and gender factors in their study concerning mountaineering. He mentioned that the death rates of men and women on high mountains are close to each other. In other words, gender does not appear as an effective variable in high mountains. Search and rescue leaders try to fulfill their duties under stress in emergency cases. It is thought that these leaders can keep their members under control and use them more effectively under these circumstances (Lois, 2003). Being under such stress continuously and working with good leaders may influence self-confidence positively and improve it both in male and in female search and rescue attendees. It is also thought that being frequently in the nature would affect self-confidence both in men and in women. The problematic situations caused by sudden environmental changes in outdoor sports activities frequently show up (Graydon and Hanson, 2010). This could be thought of as a factor improving and promoting self-confidence. Self-confidence is an important personality trait. Especially for those who engage in outdoor sports, it is an essential quality. All the information above supports our research.

Experience is a quite important feature for both mountaineering and search and rescue. We frequently face with faulty rescue operations that result in death on social media and on screens. In our study, a significant correlation was encountered between search and rescue attendees and mountaineers with 5-9 years of experience ($p<0.01$). The search and rescue attendees with 5-9 years of experience have higher self-confidence than mountaineers (Table 3). Other than this, significant differences were found in internal self-confidence between search and rescue attendees and mountaineers with 9-13 years of experience and in internal self-confidence between search and rescue attendees and mountaineers with 14-18 years of experience ($p<0.05$). As mentioned before, internal self-confidence refers to the traits of the individual such as self-love, self-knowledge, setting explicit goals, possessing the ability of positive thinking, being aware of strengths and weaknesses, easily communicating with others, sound self-expression, emotion control and risk taking (Akin, 2007). It is thought that as experience increases, self-confidence increases as well. In particular, as experience increases, internal self-confidence increases.

In other words, individuals know themselves better, think better and control their emotions better. The cases which require search and rescue are far less encountered than mountaineering activities. The reason for search and rescue attendees to have higher self-confidence in spite of this is thought to be the frequent exercises and trainings. These exercise and training activities may be improving self-confidence. The researchers have frequently addressed the matter of experience. In their research concerning high risk sports, Martha and Laurendeau (2010) arrived at the conclusion that the perceived case of being harmed upon a serious case of accident is in negative correlation with the perceived ability of the individual to manage risks and in positive correlation with injury history, sport experience and pushing limits. The self-confidence is also thought to be in positive correlation with physical condition. A good physical condition might be a factor improving self-confidence. Athletes with great experience mentioned the importance of being in good physical condition in both search and rescue and mountaineering (Gurer, 2012). In another research, Benjamin (2014) mentioned that mountaineers possess high self-confidence. Considering the necessity for search and rescue teams to be in such a condition that they can regularly and continuously perform an intervention (Collins, 2010), being in a good physical condition is one of the requirements for search and rescue. This is a factor improving self-confidence.

In our study, one of the variables for which a significant correlation was found is age (Table 4). Significant correlations were observed between mountaineers and search and rescue attendees aged 26-30 and aged 41 and above ($P<0.05$). It is seen that the self-

confidence of search and rescue attendees are higher. Particularly during the periods where physical condition is at its best level (age 26-30), it is thought that the high self-confidence of search and rescue attendees are caused by the high level of interest and enthusiasm. In some researches, it was concluded that individuals in 20s show more risky behavior and individuals in 30s or above show less risky behavior (Gretchen, 2004). The results of our study bring to mind that self-confidence is positively correlated with experience and age. This result matches with the result of our study that search and rescue attendees aged 41 and above have higher self-confidence. Again in another research, Huey et al. (2007) pointed out that mountaineers aged 40 or higher are less likely to reach the peak. They emphasized that young mountaineers could reach the peak more frequently. As can be seen, the age factor appears an important criterion in extreme activities. Considering the age intervals, self-confidence seems to show change as age increases. As the cause for this change, the factors such as physical competence, frequency of attending mountain climbing or rescue operations and team cohesion can be shown. In this context, as an element improving self-confidence, the researchers showed that individuals can benefit from attending outdoor sports activities and attain positive approaches for improving self-competence (Kalkan, 2012).

Another finding of our research is that marital status has an effect on self-confidence (Table 5). The significant correlation was found in internal and total self-confidence for married search and rescue attendees and only in internal self-confidence for single search and rescue attendees. In other words, traits such as self-love, self-knowledge, setting explicit goals, possess the ability of positive thinking (Akın, 2007) are correlated with marital status. As opposed to what was expected, the self-confidence of married search and rescue attendees is higher than that of married mountaineers and this is a surprising result. According to this, family does not adversely affect the self-confidence of an individual who engage in search and rescue operations. On the contrary, it was thought that married athletes would show an avoidant approach against such risky situations. It was pointed out in researches that the risky sports are conducted more frequently by single individuals. This could be caused by the fact that single people have more free time. Jack and Roman (1998) mentioned that people who attend in high-risk unusual sportive activities, especially mountaineers and parachutists, possess higher levels of tendency to seek general and unusual excitement than those who attend in low-risk usual sports. It would not be wrong to say that the high self-confidence of mountaineers and search and rescue attendees are caused by that they spend more time nature. In particular, single people are able to spare more time for risky sports since their responsibility limits are lower. It is thought that this variable is affected by factors such as how mountaineers spend time

in their daily lives, their circle of friends, climbing partners and work life. Risk-taking can be an independent variable of sports. The spiritual comforting offered by extreme sports cannot be ignored (Olivier, 2006). All these results reveal the importance of self-confidence for challenging sports such as mountaineering and search and rescue. While marital status affects mountaineering and search and rescue, it also increases self-confidence for both branches.

In conclusion, it is showed that those who engage in mountaineering and search and rescue operations have high self-confidence. Besides, search and rescue attendees have higher self-confidence than mountaineers. Mountaineering and search and rescue attendees require self-confidence due to their inherent risks. Moreover, the responsibility of the group increases these risks. The reason for the necessity of self-confidence is the existence of danger in the activities. It is revealed that individuals who engage in search and rescue operations have higher self-confidence than mountaineers. It is thought that decision-making in emergency cases and the accuracy of decisions affect the level of self-confidence. Especially experience and age are important for self-confidence in these activities. Improving self-confidence and avoiding risks and dangers accordingly can be achieved only through going to the mountains and getting inside the nature. In light of this, regular mountaineering activities search and rescue exercise and training contribute to improving self-confidence. Depending on experience, in mountaineering and in search and rescue, self-confidence is thought to improve abilities such as risk-taking, decision-making, evaluation and judgment. It is suggested that being in good physical condition would be important in improving self-confidence. Our study is important for it may shed light on new studies. Analyzing the emotion of self-confidence related to different outdoor sports would enrich literature.

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